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WAYS TO INCREASE THE COMMUNICATIVE ABILITIES OF EDUCATORS

Abstract: This article describes the evaluation system based on the processes implemented as a result of methodical support.

Key words: information and communication technologies, digital technology, cognitive activity, digitization, education, virtual world, development, globalization, motivation, integration.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada uslubiy yordam natijasida amalga oshirilgan jarayonlarga asoslangan baholash tizimi tasvirlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, raqamli texnologiya, kognitiv faoliyat, raqamlashtirish, ta'lim, virtual dunyo, rivojlanish, globallashtirish, motivatsiya, integratsiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье описывается система оценки, основанная на процессах, реализуемых в результате методического обеспечения.

Ключевые слова: информационно-коммуникационные технологии, цифровые технологии, познавательная деятельность, цифровизация, образование, виртуальный мир виртуальный мир, развитие, глобализация, мотивация, интеграция.

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The essence of the oral examination is that the teacher determines the level of mastery of the students based on the content of the subject studied. Oral examination is carried out based on the question-and-answer method of checking students' knowledge. This method is sometimes called the interview method. In the oral examination, the teacher divides the studied topic into separate parts and asks students questions from each of them. However, in order to develop students' speech and to have deep and solid knowledge, they can be asked to completely recall this or the previous topic. In many subjects, the oral examination is completed based on the organization of written exercises for students' answers. They give an example to prove their answer. They write these examples on the board and analyze them syntactically and grammatically. Oral examination of mathematics, physics and chemistry is solved according to the rules based on the purpose of assessing practical skills and skills. Despite its widespread use and effectiveness, oral examination in monitoring and evaluating students' knowledge has some disadvantages. Therefore, various forms are used to monitor the students' knowledge and ensure the success of the assessment.

An oral public examination is an oral questioning of students, who answer questions directed at the group. The answers to such a check will be short. This type of questioning provides control for most students and activates the whole group, but does not

increase student speech. Such defects are not visible in individual inquiries. But in this form of asking, it is very difficult to achieve the full performance of other students in the group.

In combined (accelerated) testing, the teacher calls several students to the blackboard at the same time, one gives an oral answer, and 3-4 students do written work on cards, etc. This is a complex method of examination, which requires the teacher to have sufficient experience and to be able to distribute his attention to all the students in the group.

Written examination is one of the most effective methods of monitoring and evaluating students' knowledge, skills, and abilities, and allows to evaluate their creative abilities. The essence of this method is that the teacher controls and evaluates the knowledge of students after passing a specific subject or a certain section of the curriculum. A written test allows you to do homework, that is, to write an essay, as well as to perform various supervised and independent tasks. In this process, a lot of work and time is spent for the teacher to familiarize himself with the completed work and check its quality.

1. Examination based on the completion of practical tasks. It can consist of observing the correctness of the performed practical actions (sports, labor actions) or relying on the obtained results. Monitoring of all the student's activities during the entire lesson is a special type of examination, which ends with a score for the student's participation in the lesson. This encourages the student to always move and be active.

2. It is known that rating control is widely used in the education system today. Rating means evaluation, arrangement, classification, evaluation of any event according to a predetermined scale.

3. Scaling - modeling specific processes using a number system. Its various techniques help convert qualitative descriptions into quantitative changes.

4. Along with the above-mentioned methods of taking into account the educational activity of students based on rating control, the test method is also effectively used. The test survey has been used effectively not only to determine the level of knowledge, skills and qualifications of students, but also in the process of selective admission of applicants to higher educational institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan since 1993.

A test is a test tool that allows you to determine the level of a certain condition in qualitative and quantitative indicators based on a specific goal.

A number of advantages of the test are evident in pedagogical practice. They are:

- 1) less time spent on control;
- 2) the possibility of determining the level of theoretical and practical knowledge in objective conditions;
- 3) it is possible to organize supervision with a large number of students at the same time;
- 4) short-term verification of knowledge results by the teacher;
- 5) all students are asked questions of the same complexity and the same conditions are created for them.

Since the five-point evaluation system is still used in school practice today, pedagogues are looking for ways to increase the

motivational role of this system. Several methods are used in this regard. In particular:

Expressing values with addition and subtraction signs. The current rules for keeping class journals do not allow the use of expressive marks. Therefore, the pedagogue makes a compromise and puts accurate grades in the class journal, and records pluses and minuses in his personal notebook;

Completing the number with a point value (additional value). This method has no instructional prohibitions, but it is rarely used by pedagogues, because this method requires spending more time during the lesson, which is already scarce;

Teacher writing notes for parents along with grading in the diary. This method is based on strengthening the student's responsibility towards the family. If the following situation is not taken into account, there is nothing unusual about it. Acquaintance with the content of the entries in the diary shows that they are mostly negative in content. It is known that negative thoughts destroy students' motivation to study. According to the results of the research, negative notes in the diary are the factor that reduces the motivation to study among 5th-6th graders.

Communicative motive - attitude, opinion of peers. Students cannot be indifferent to the attitudes and opinions of their peers. A teacher should be able to use such a factor, but it is not appropriate to abuse it, because such an approach also weakens the motivation of students to learn. At the beginning of the 19th and 20th centuries, such a rule prevailed in gymnasiums: a student can be praised in front of the team, but not put down. Even today, it is not without benefit to follow this rule in educational practice.

Strengthening the communicative effect, successes and failures of their classmates, to which consists in teaching students to feel the help them.

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